

microkjeldahl method, and ammonia volatilization estimated.

Ammonia volatilization losses in the

first 4 d after fertilizer application were highest with *Acacia arabica* and lowest with deep placed USG (see table).

Ammonia volatilization was higher with plant residues (more than 20%) than with urea. □

Effect of sowing time and planting method on rice yield per day

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A 3-yr study (1975-77) evaluated the effect of sowing time and method on rice (Ribe) productivity per day. Main plots were early, normal, and late sowing; subplots were planting methods, transplanting, broadcasting, and drilling. Subplots were 40 m².

In general, yield decreased with

Effect of sowing time and planting method on yield. Izmir, Turkey, 1975-77. ^a

Duration (d)	21 May		Duration (d)	4 Jun		Duration (d)	20 Jun	
	Yield			Yield			Yield	
	t/ha	kg/d		t/ha	kg/d		t/ha	kg/d
127	5.1	40.2	140	Transplanting 5.6	40.0	130	5.1	39.2
120	4.5	37.5	117	Drilling 4.4	37.6	112	4.4	39.3
124	5.7	46.0	115	Broadcasting 5.7	49.6	111	5.1	45.9

^a Duration = day from sowing or transplanting to harvest. LSD at 5%: yield = 0.45, duration = 2.3, yield per day = 6.10.

delayed sowing (see table). Yields were higher with early season broadcasting

and lower with drilling in all sowing times. □

Efficacy of *Azospirillum brasilense* in increasing rice yield

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Azospirillum brasilense Tarrand et al. colonizes rice roots and fixes atmospheric N in soil. Its efficacy depends on the pre-inoculum soil N status. We studied the effect of *A. brasilense* in the field at different N (urea) application levels.

Peat-based *A. brasilense* inoculum mixed with well-powdered farmyard manure (2 kg inoculum + 15 kg farmyard manure/ ha) was uniformly

Grain and straw yield response to *A. brasilense* inoculation. Aduthurai, India.

Dose of nitrogenous fertilizer (kg N/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)			% increase ^a	Straw yield (t/ha)		
	Without <i>A. brasilense</i>	With <i>A. brasilense</i>			Without <i>A. brasilense</i>	With <i>A. brasilense</i>	% increase ^a
0	3.1	3.1		0 ns	4.5	5.9	31*
25	3.5	3.8		9*	6.0	6.5	8 ns
50	4.1	4.4		7*	6.0	1.6	27*
75	3.6	4.4		22*	5.9	8.3	41*
100	4.3	4.1		ns	6.8	7.7	13*
CD (0.05)		0.2					

^a = significant difference, ns = not significant.

broadcast in the field after urea application. Roots of ADT36 seedlings were soaked in 1 kg *A. brasilense*/400 liters water solution for 20 min before transplanting.

Inoculation increased grain and straw yield over urea alone, particularly at 75 kg N/ha (see table). □

Phosphate sources for lowland rice

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We compared the efficiency of seven phosphate sources in a randomized block design replicated three times

during 1980 and 1981 wet seasons. The soil was clay loam (Typic Aquept) with pH 5.6, 0.65% organic C, and 9 kg Olsen's P/ha.

Phosphate sources were single superphosphate (6.9% P), Mussorie rock phosphate (9.5% P), mixture of single superphosphate and Mussorie rock phosphate at 3:1 and 1:1 P, urea ammonium phosphate (28-12-0 NPK), diammonium phosphate (18-20.6-0

NPK), and seedling root dip phosphate slurry prepared with single superphosphate, soil, water, and fresh cow dung at 1:2:3:1. We used 8.6 kg P/ha for the phosphate slurry and 17.8 kg P/ha for soil application. Pankaj was planted with 60-17.8-25 kg NPK/ha.

Single superphosphate and Mussorie rock phosphate at 1:1 gave better yields than 5 other treatments